

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF FUTURE ECONOMISTS

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***Abstract.** The article discusses issues related to diagnosing the level of development of foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence of future bachelors in economics. The article describes the experimental and statistical data of the ascertaining stage of the pedagogical experiment. Criteria and indicators are defined, and the results of diagnosing the level of development of foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence of future economists are presented.*

***Keywords:** future economists, criteria, foreign language training, diagnostics, professional competence.*

INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of the fourth industrial revolution, not only a radical transformation of business processes and production is taking place, but also society as a whole. One of the key strategic directions in the development of modern society is the digitalization of all social and production processes, which requires theoretical understanding and the search for ways to improve the training of future bachelors in economics. The economic sector will require specialists capable of continuous learning and integration of knowledge from various fields of science into professional activities to solve complex problems and proactively work in a global context.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today, the development of linguistic and professional abilities of students at non-linguistic universities is due to the growing tendency of professional activities towards international standards. This influenced the reorganization of the labor market and identified the task of training specialists to carry out communicative activities in the modern information environment as one of the priorities of the lifelong education system. Higher professional educational institutions play an important role in this process, since the level of training of future specialists determines socio-economic, scientific, technical and cultural progress. This is especially true when training specialists in economics, in whose work it is always important to obtain an extensive amount of knowledge that will make it possible in the future to solve problems of a new direction and increased complexity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the most important criterion for assessing the quality of education is the result - the formation of skills, abilities and positive motivation among students, and the indicator is efficiency in the entire educational process, the pedagogical problem of diagnosing the development of students' competencies arises, without which it is impossible to monitor the quality of professional training of future graduates of the Institute Economics and management. The practical value of the study is explained by the fact that its results contribute to solving this problem. The theoretical significance is due to the transition of the modern educational process to the e-learning format, in which the issues of effective communication in a foreign language in the online environment and assessing the effectiveness of these tools, as well as the readiness of students to use them when communicating in a foreign language, become relevant. The scientific novelty of this study lies in

the fact that when trying to solve the pedagogical problem of diagnosing the development of students’ competencies, we get the opportunity to assess not only the level of knowledge of a foreign language among future bachelors of economics, but also to determine the extent to which students are ready to use a foreign language for specialized communication in the professional field.

The relevance of the study is explained by the social objectives set and lies in identifying ways to improve the quality of foreign language training for economic specialists.

Purpose of the study: to identify the initial level of development of foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence of future economists in the conditions of e-learning.

Research objectives: based on the results of analysis and generalization of scientific and theoretical data, to identify criteria and determine indicators, diagnostic methods for the initial level of development of foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence of future economists in the conditions of e-learning.

Table 1

Criteria, indicators, diagnostic methods for the initial level of development of foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence

<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Diagnostic techniques</i>
<i>Motivational</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – presence of a stable interest in teaching a foreign language for professional purposes; – readiness to use a foreign language in the professional sphere; – awareness by future bachelor-economists of the need to master foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence for successful professional activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – a questionnaire to track the level of motivation to learn a foreign language; – observation to identify the individual characteristics of students, their interests, capabilities
<i>Cognitive and content</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – knowledge of a foreign language in the field of finance and economics; – possession of communication skills and strategies and their successful application in professional activities; – mastery of new information technologies and Internet resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – the use of information and communication technologies in teaching a foreign language, such as electronic testing programs, online courses, research projects; – testing to determine the level of foreign language proficiency; – search and analysis of information in electronic resources (scientific articles, lectures, reports, scientific journals) and use of electronic educational resources (online courses, video lessons, interactive games and tests)
<i>Communicative-activity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – availability of skills to work with various electronic resources and modern information and communication technologies in a foreign language; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – electronic tests and test materials, which include lexical and grammatical tests and tasks for reading and understanding texts in a foreign language;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – the student’s ability to apply knowledge and skills, understand and interpret various types of texts, participate in various communicative situations and express his thoughts and ideas in a foreign language in the process of developing foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – modeling situations of professional communication in a foreign language: writing letters, drawing up reports, preparing presentations, situational games; – communicative task to determine the level of foreign language proficiency: exchange of information, discussion, debate, presentation, report
<i>Reflective</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – the ability to independently plan, organize, control and analyze one’s communication activities; – the ability to introspect, self-assessment and adapt one’s communication strategy depending on the situation; – the ability to form a positive attitude towards learning a foreign language and communicative activities in a foreign language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – self-analysis of the level of development of foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence and educational and professional achievements (self-analysis and self-assessment assessment sheets); – analysis/self-analysis of students’ oral presentation

The essence of both the competence-based and personality-oriented approaches are the competencies of students formed as a result of the educational process, which represent the integration of knowledge, skills, experience and combine the abilities and motivation of students.

Competencies are universal concepts, integrative qualities of a person, reflecting the ability to solve life and professional problems, with the help of which the desired results are achieved. Competencies are dynamic, and, being components in the structure of a person’s personal and professional qualities, they are not an immutable characteristic and are capable of change and improvement.

Foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence of bachelors of the Institute of Economics and Management is represented by a multicomponent system that allows the implementation of such competencies as foreign language linguistic - grammar, vocabulary, phonetics; communicative – communication in the professional sphere; professional – professional and personal qualities of students. Thus, we understand the foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence of bachelors of the Institute of Economics as an integral characteristic of business and personal qualities, abilities and readiness to carry out effective foreign language professional communication in the professional field in order to implement functions corresponding to the chosen direction of study [5].

As a result of the study, criteria were identified and indicators and diagnostic methods were determined for the initial level of development of foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence of future economists in the conditions of e-learning in the do.sevsu system. ru.

The main methodological position in the formation of communication skills in future economists in the process of learning a foreign language is the focus of pedagogical activities on ensuring the quality of education of future economists.

In our research we rely on

– linguoculturological approach, since it is determined by the objective connection of a person with culture as a system of values;

– activity approach, since “interaction” is one of the holistic and essential characteristics of education; personal approach, since the content and nature of communication depend on their personal development.

During the research process, various methods were used: analysis of literature on the research problem; analysis of the federal state standard for higher education in economic areas.

The quality of student education is characterized not simply by the amount of knowledge, but by the readiness to establish relationships with other people, which is an indispensable attribute of any person in modern society. A foreign language provides powerful resources for the development of professional competence of specialists, since professional competence is an integral component of an individual’s life competence [3]. These resources are associated with the possibilities of forming such personal aspects as: socio-cultural competence (which is associated with the expansion of ways a person interacts with the world thanks to the development of an additional language code of communication and mastery of reality); development of interactive strategies for interacting with the world (due to the development of social roles, which follows from the communicative-role orientation of the process of teaching a foreign language) [6]. “The human factor in a partnership is decisive, therefore, it can be argued that the key factor in the success of such an association of partners is their mutual trust.”

As a result of studying the discipline “Foreign Language” in economic areas, the student masters the following general cultural competencies: the ability to construct oral and written speech logically, logically and logically; knowledge of one of the foreign languages at a level that ensures effective professional activity.

To develop communication skills, tasks of a problem-solving and creative nature are used with an emphasis on role-playing. The communicative and performing skill of a specialist is manifested as two interrelated and relatively independent skills to find a communicative structure adequate to the topic of communication that corresponds to the purpose of communication, and the ability to realize oneself in communication. In the communicative and performing skills of an individual, the skills of emotional and psychological self-regulation are manifested, which creates the mood in communication [1].

An important factor contributing to the education of a multicultural personality [2] is authenticity, which should concern all aspects of the process of teaching a foreign language, from the created situations of foreign language interpersonal communication to the teaching aids used in practical classes. Students should be guided to independently search for authentic information on the topics discussed.

An important skill is the critical analysis and evaluation of educational and methodological packages, including electronic educational resources. “One cannot help but note the importance and relevance of the ability to conduct a discussion” [4]. Therefore, we consider the discussion method as one of the effective methods for developing communicative skills among economic students as an effective means of teaching students business foreign language communication. This method also contributes to the development of a communicative culture, which is represented by a set of norms and forms of interaction and carries behavioral values.

So, for example, when considering the topic “Marketing management”, the dialogue “Director of a company discusses with the Product Manager the market position of some of their

product” is played out, which is accompanied by a business game in the form of a conversation in a real situation:

Reproduce the parts of the dialogue where the Director and the Product Manager discuss:

- 1) the position of their major product on the market;
- 2) the change-over to new products;
- 3) the sales support for the new products.

The situation “Canadian agency firm entered into contact with Soyuz export to discuss the lines of their future business” is accompanied by the following task:

Reproduce the parts of the dialogue where the two businessmen discuss:

- 1) the possibility of granting the agents exclusive rights for 3 years;
- 2) the option of the principals to terminate the agreement.

Situation “Canadian agency firm entered into contact with Soyuz export to discuss the lines of their fu-

ture business" involves the following tasks:

Reproduce the parts of the dialogue where the two businessmen discuss:

- 1) the possibility of granting the agents exclusive rights for 3 years;
- 2) the option of the principals to terminate the agreement. Act out a similar dialogue.

It is very important to develop the following indicators: the ability to clearly explain your thoughts; readiness to interact, ability to resolve conflicts, tolerance, responsibility, ability to adequately perceive foreign language information from partners in intercultural interaction. All these indicators together represent communicative competence based on the practical preparedness of the student’s personality.

Using all of the above in practice, we propose to subordinate linguistic material to the task of individual speech intention. In foreign language classes, it is necessary to develop in students such important qualities as the ability to communicate, defend their opinion, persuade, and master a communicative culture. After all, organizational and communication skills are the most important components of the effectiveness of professional activities. The uncertainty of the modern economic environment sets the importance of “intercompany interaction and a conscious choice of development strategy, based on taking into account the interests of selected participants” [8].

CONCLUSION

It is important to note that e-learning is an effective tool in developing the professional competence of future economists. A significant portion of students positively evaluate the use of electronic educational materials, online courses and interactive platforms in the learning process. The majority of respondents noted an increase in the level of independence and self-organization in the process of studying the subject, as well as an increase in motivation for learning. However, e-learning also has some disadvantages, such as reduced social interaction and lack of participation in live communication with teachers and colleagues. This can reduce student motivation and lead to a decrease in learning effectiveness. Therefore, to achieve the best results, it is necessary to continue to research and develop new pedagogical technologies and methods for using e-learning tools in the process of training future economists. Ultimately, based on our research, we can conclude that electronic educational resources, electronic training courses and e-learning in general have great potential and can become a key tool in increasing the level of development of

professional competence of future economists, subject to optimal organization and application of such teaching methods.

REFERENCES

1. Order No. 1632-r dated July 28, 2017. Available at: <http://government.ru/docs/28653/>
2. Vvedensky V.N. Professional competence of a teacher: a manual for teachers. St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg branch of the publishing house "Prosveshchenie", 2014.
3. Zimnyaya I.A. Key competencies are a new paradigm for educational results. Higher education. 2013; No. 5: 34–42.
4. Markova A.K. Psychology of professionalism. Moscow: International Humanitarian Foundation “Knowledge”, 2016.
5. Verbitsky A.A., Larionova O.G. Personal and competence approaches in education: problems of integration. Moscow: Logos, 2019.
6. Gez N.I. Formation of communicative competence as an object of foreign methodological research. Foreign languages at school. 2015; No. 2: 17–24.
7. Mironseva S.S. Formation of foreign language professionally oriented competence of future managers using electronic educational resources. Dissertation... candidate of pedagogical sciences. Yalta, 2019.
8. Khutorskoy A.V. Methodology of personality-oriented training. How to train everyone differently? Moscow: VLADOS-PRESS, 2015.